

***In vitro* degradation of poly[(r)-3-hydroxybutyrate] and BIOPOL™ by marine-derived fungi**

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Abstract. As part of efforts to conserve global resources and reduce pollution, the search for new bio-synthetic/biodegradable materials remains an urgent task. Poly[(R)-3-hydroxyalkanoates] (PHAs) are synthesized by bacteria and display thermoplastic properties. The most common bacterial bio-synthetic PHAs are poly[(R)-3-hydroxybutyrate] (PHB), poly[(R)-3-hydroxyvalerate] (PHV) and their copolymers. PHB and PHV are already commercially produced and used as BIOPOL™ (ICI) for packaging purposes. Oceans and estuaries often serve as major landfills and fungi are an important component of their biodegradation microbiota. In order to characterize the role of fungi in marine biodegradation processes, a simple degradation test suitable for fungi in partially simulated marine conditions had to be developed. Thirty-two strains of yeasts and 102 strains of mycelial fungi isolated from marine habitats and belonging to different systematic and ecological groups were tested for their ability to degrade PHAs. Only approximately 4.5% of the strains were able to degrade BIOPOL™ and about 6.7% depolymerized pure PHB homopolymers. This is in sharp contrast to the results of our previous experiments with 143 strains of terrestrial fungi which showed that more than 55% were able to degrade BIOPOL™. Among ascomycetous fungi, one strain of *Asteromyces cruciatus*, one strain of *Candida guilliermondii*, and two strains of *Debaryomyces hansenii* were able to degrade PHB or both PHB and BIOPOL™. Active basidiomycetous fungi were represented by one strain of *Nia vibrissa* and one strain of *Rhodosporidium sphaerocarpum* that were able to depolymerize PHB, but not BIOPOL™.

Key words: biodegradation, BIOPOL, marine fungal isolates, PHA, PHB, Polyhydroxyalkanoates, screening.

INTRODUCTION

The current global decrease in our natural fossil resources has stimulated increased interest in the search for renewable, bio-synthetic raw materials. Furthermore, current concerns about global environmental pollution associated with petrochemical-based plastics has inspired investigations into possible options for the replacement of such non-degradable synthetic polymers with acceptable bio-degradable substitutes (Hartley 1987; Lafferty et al. 1988; Anderson and Dawes 1990; Brandl et al. 1990; Abe et al. 1995). In some bacteria PHAs constitute a major carbon and energy storage material (Holmes 1988; Fuller 1990). PHAs have generated increased research interest in recent years because of their biodegradability, biocompatibility, and excellent mechanical properties compared with traditional nondegradable

thermoplastics, such as polypropylene and polyethylene. Poly[(R)-3-hydroxybutyrate] (PHB) is the most extensively studied type in the PHA family and has been used successfully in the medical and packing fields as a renewable and biodegradable plastic (Guo et al. 2016). Recently, PHB and PHV, often co-polymerized as PHB-co-HV, were demonstrated to possess interesting thermoplastic properties. Thus, these biopolymers have attracted great industrial interest. BIOPOL™, a new biodegradable plastic material, is one such copolymer and is already being produced on a large scale for use as packaging material (ICI, Imperial Chemical Industries, England, 1990).

For the environment, one of the most important properties of PHAs is their ability to undergo complete microbial bio-degradation to CO₂, water and energy (Byrom 1990; ICI 1990). In addition, due to a decline in production costs, PHAs are today used more and more for the production of

biodegradable containers, packages, and disposable dishware and household goods. Therefore, PHAs are ecologically important alternative materials that can replace synthetic plastics (Thị Vân Anh 2010; Angelini et al. 2014). In the natural environment, PHAs are decomposed by degrading microorganisms to carbon dioxide and water under aerobic conditions, or methane and water under anaerobic conditions. (Matavulj et al. 1995, 2006; Boyandin et al. 2012a, 2012b). Enzymolysis by PHB-depolymerase has been considered to be the root cause of PHB degradation (Guo et al. 2016).

PHAs have been shown to be completely bio-degradable by bacteria both in culture or under environmental (terrestrial, freshwater, anthropogenic) conditions (Macrae and Wilkinson 1958; Merrick and Doudoroff 1964; Delafield et al. 1965; Lusti and Doudoroff 1966; Hippe und Schlegel 1967; Fedulova et al. 1980; Tanio et al. 1982; Nakayama et al. 1985; Fukui et al. 1988; Janssen and Harfoot 1990; Manna and Paul 2000; González García et al. 2013). However, few reports have addressed PHA bio-degradation in marine environments (Akmal et al. 2003; Rutkowska et al. 2008; Rydz 2015; Volova et al. 2015).

In early reports on microbial PHAs and PHA-based plastic decomposers, fungi received little attention and (with a few exceptions) were mostly neglected (Delafield et al. 1965; Lepidi et al. 1972). However, in recent decades molds, yeasts and even mushrooms have attracted greater attention with respect to plastic biodegradation (Holmes 1985; McLellan and Halling 1988; Dave et al. 1990a, 1990b; Matavulj and Molitoris 1990, 1991a, 1991b, 1991c; 1992; Matavulj 1991; Matavulj et al. 1992; Neumeier et al. 1994a, 1994b; Kim and Rhee 2003). Fungi are an important part of the biodegradation microbiota, playing a very active role in mineralization of organic matter and in element cycling. Because they are equipped with extracellular multienzyme complexes, fungi are often highly efficient “bio-degradation machines”, especially for the breakdown of natural polymeric compounds. In addition, due to their fast-growing hyphal systems they are also able to colonize substrates rapidly, and to transport and redistribute nutrients within their mycelium (Brucato and Wong 1991; Cooney et al. 1993; Andersen et al. 2011).

Mycorrhizal fungi are also an important component of soil life and soil chemistry. Fungi possess important degradative capabilities that have implications for the recycling of recalcitrant polymers, and for the elimination of hazardous wastes from the environment (Joutey et al. 2013; Katanić et al. 2013, 2015; Pilipović et al. 2014). Previously we reported that, unlike bacteria which degrade only the surface of organic substrates, through the use of their hyphae mycelial fungi are able to penetrate deeply into organic materials. Moreover, being equipped with a broader spectrum of enzymes, they are able to efficiently degrade and decompose all natural polymers (Matavulj et al. 1992, 1995, 1997, 2000; Rohrmann and Molitoris 1992; Gassner and Matavulj 1997; Molitoris et al. 1997; Matavulj and Molitoris 1999; Karaman

et al. 2012). The available data on fungal bio-degradation of PHAs or PHA-based plastics are summarized chronologically in Table 1.

The ultimate fate of many organic materials is mineralization by microorganisms. Ever-increasing demand for materials leads to a concomitant increase in waste production. The fact that marine environments (sea- and estuarine waters, sea-bed sediments, coastal sand/rock/soil areas), often serve today as major landfills (O’Brine and Thompson 2010) means that new generations of bio-synthetic plastics likely must be degraded in marine environments (Pruter 1987; Doi et al. 1992; Mukai and Doi 1995; Tsui and Suzuyoshi 2002). Marine fungi would thus be expected to participate significantly in waste bio-plastic materials decomposition.

Obligate marine fungi are those that grow and sporulate exclusively in a marine or estuarine habitat; facultative marine fungi are those from freshwater and terrestrial milieus that are able to grow and possibly also sporulate in a marine environment (Kohlmeyer and Kohlmeyer 1979). Marine fungi grow on a wide variety of substrata: ranging from wood, sediments, mud, soil, sand, algae, coral, decaying leaves (e.g. mangroves), intertidal grasses and living animals, to the guts of crustaceans or other organisms. The need for a concerted effort to investigate the biodiversity and role of marine fungi globally and on as many substrata as possible has already been emphasized (Hyde 1989; Matavulj and Molitoris 1992; Hyde et al. 1998).

Fungi possess important bio-degradative capabilities that have implications for recycling recalcitrant polymers (e.g. lignin) and for the elimination of hazardous wastes from the environment (Mohapatra 2006). In addition to aromatic and aliphatic hydrocarbon compounds, microfungi may transform numerous other aromatic pollutants cometabolically: including polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, various pesticides, and plasticizers (Joutey et al. 2013). Some marine-derived fungi were even reported as potential catalysts for bio-remediation of oil spills and other potential pollutants (Cooney et al. 1992; Matavulj and Molitoris 2009; Volova et al. 2010).

It is currently well-accepted that fungi play significant roles in microbial bio-degradation processes. However, their role in the bio-transformation of allochthonous organic matter – particularly in marine habitats – remains largely unknown. In order to address this gap in our current knowledge, a simple screening method for fungal bio-degradation of BIOPOL™ and its components (PHB homopolymer and triacetin) must be developed. The method should provide at least semi-quantitative data and enable screening large numbers of fungal marine isolates under partially simulated marine conditions (seawater mineral composition, level of salinity, pH). Screening of bio-degradation of PHAs by fungi isolated from marine environments should elucidate the capacity of marine fungal population to participate in biodegradation of novel PHA-based pollutants reaching ma-

Table 1. Chronological review of fungal species degrading poly[(R)-3-hydroxyalkanoates].

Species	Taxon	Strain	Substrate	Reference
<i>Penicillium simplicissimum</i>	A		PHB	McLellan and Halling 1988a,b
<i>Eupenicillium</i> sp.	A	IMI 300465	PHB	McLellan and Halling 1988a
<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	A		PHB	Püchner 1988
<i>Penicillium funiculosum</i> Syn. <i>Talaromyces funiculosus</i>	A		PHB	Dave et al. 1990a,b
<i>Penicillium funiculosum</i> Syn. <i>Talaromyces funiculosus</i>	A		PHB	Brucato and Wong 1991
<i>Penicillium simplicissimum</i>	A		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Penicillium atrovenetum</i>	A		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Trichoderma polysporum</i>	A		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Collybia peronata</i>	B		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Lentinus edodes</i>	B		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i>	B		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Serpula lacrymans</i>	B		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Nectria episphaeria</i>	A		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Mucor hiemalis</i>	Z		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	Z		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Phlyctochytrium africanum</i>	C		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Phlyctochytrium palustre</i>	C		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Dictyostelium discoideum</i>	My-Am		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Physarum polycephalum</i>	My-Am		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991a
<i>Polyporus circinatus</i>	B		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1992
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	Z		BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1992
<i>Penicillium simplicissimum</i>	A	IMI 300465	BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1992
<i>Cephalosporium</i> sp.	A		BIOPOL	Matavulj et al. 1992b; 2000
<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	A		BIOPOL	Matavulj et al. 1992b; 2000
<i>Verticillium</i> sp.	A		BIOPOL	Matavulj et al. 1992b; 2000
<i>Cladosporium</i> sp.	A		BIOPOL	Matavulj et al. 1992b; 2000
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	A		BIOPOL	Matavulj et al. 1992b; 2000
<i>Penicillium restrictum</i>	A		PHB	Mergaert et al. 1992
<i>Penicillium orchrocloron</i>	A		PHB	Mergaert et al. 1992
<i>Penicillium daleae</i>	A		PHB	Mergaert et al. 1992
<i>Aspergillus penicilloides</i>	A		PHB	Mergaert et al. 1992
<i>Paecilomyces marquandii</i>	A		PHB	Mergaert et al. 1992
<i>Penicillium adametzii</i>	A		PHB	Mergaert et al. 1992
<i>Acremonium</i> sp.	A		PHB; 3-PHB/3-PHV	Mergaert et al. 1993
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	A		PHB	Mergaert et al. 1993, 1994
<i>Verticillium leptobactrum</i>	A		PHB	Mergaert et al. 1994
<i>Penicillium chermisinum</i>	A		PHB	Mergaert et al. 1995
<i>Penicillium janthinellum</i>	A		PHB	Mergaert et al. 1995
<i>Penicillium simplicissimum</i>	A		PHB	Mergaert et al. 1995
<i>Penicillium funiculosum</i>	A		PHB	Oda et al. 1995
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	A		PHB	Hocking et al. 1996
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	A		PHB	Scherer 1996
<i>Paecilomyces lilacinus</i>	A	D218	PHB	Oda et al. 1997
<i>Penicillium pinophilum</i>	A	ATCC 9644	PHB	Han et al. 1998
<i>Rhizopus delamar</i>	Z		(R)-3-HB-co-HH	Abe et al. 1995
<i>Penicillium chrysosporium</i>	A		3-PHB/3-PHV	Renstad et al. 1999
<i>Penicillium simplicissimum</i>	A		3-PHB/3-PHV	Renstad et al. 1999
<i>Phanerochaete chrysosporium</i>	A		3-PHB/3-PHV	Renstad et al. 1999
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	A	M2A	PHB	Scherer et al. 1999
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	A		PHB-co-PHV	Eldsäter 1999
<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	A		PHB	Sanchez et al. 2000
<i>Thermoascus aurantiacus</i>	A	IFO 31910	PHB	Sanchez et al. 2000
<i>Aspergillus ustus</i>	A	T-221	PHB	Gonda et al. 2000
<i>Paecilomyces</i> sp.	A		PHB	Savenkova et al. 2000
<i>Cephalosporium</i> sp.	A		PHB	Savenkova et al. 2000
<i>Trichoderma</i> sp.	A		PHB	Savenkova et al. 2000
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	A		PHB	Savenkova et al. 2000

Table 1. Chronological review of fungal species degrading poly[(R)-3-hydroxyalkanoates]. (continued)

Species	Taxon	Strain	Substrate	Reference
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	A		PHB	Scherer et al. 2000
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	A	Pdf1	PHB	Iyer et al. 2000
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	A	LAR 11	PHB	Kim et al. 2000
<i>Penicillium minioluteum</i>	A	LAR 14	PHB	Kim et al. 2000
<i>Penicillium pinophilum</i>	A	LAR 15	PHB	Kim et al. 2000
<i>Penicillium pinophilum</i>	A	LAR 13	PHB	Kim et al. 2000
<i>Penicillium simplicissimum</i>	A	IFO 6345	PHB	Miyazaki et al. 2000
<i>Trichoderma reesei</i>	A		PHA polymers	Cutright, 2002
<i>Paecilomyces lilacinus</i>	A	F4-5	PHB-co-PHV	Sang et al. 2002
<i>Paecilomyces farinosus</i>	A	F4-7	PHB-co-PHV	Sang et al. 2002
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	A	F1-3	PHB-co-PHV	Sang et al. 2002
<i>Penicillium simplicissimum</i>	A	LAR13	PHB	Han and Kim 2002
<i>Emercellopsis minima</i>	A	W2	PHB; 3-PHB/3-PHV	Kim et al. 2002
<i>Penicillium funiculosum</i>	A	ATCC 11797	PHB-co-HV/PHEMA	Gracida et al. 2004
<i>Syn. Talaromyces funiculosus</i>				
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	A	DS9701-09a	PHB	Liu et al. 2006
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	A	DS9713a-01	PHB	Ci et al. 2006
<i>Penicillium funiculosum</i>	A		PHB	Hisano et al. 2006
<i>Syn. Talaromyces funiculosus</i>				
<i>Paecilomyces lilacinus</i>	A	F4-5	PHB	Sang et al. 2006
<i>Syn. Purpureocillium lilacinum</i>			PHB-co-PHV	
<i>Penicillium funiculosum</i>	A		PHB	Numata et al. 2007
<i>Syn. Talaromyces funiculosus</i>				
<i>Penicillium simplicissimum</i>	A	T-154	BIOPOL	Matavuly and Molitoris 2009
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	A	DS9701-D2	PHB	Zhou et al. 2009
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	A	202	PHB	Bhatt et al. 2010
<i>Malbranchea</i> sp.	A		PHB; 3-PHB/3-PHV	Volova et al. 2010
<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	A		PHB; 3-PHB/3-PHV	Volova et al. 2010
<i>Verticillium</i> sp.	A		PHB; 3-PHB/3-PHV	Volova et al. 2010
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	A		PHB; 3-PHB/3-PHV	Volova et al. 2010
<i>Trichoderma</i> sp.	A		PHB; 3-PHB/3-PHV	Volova et al. 2010
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	Z		PHB; 3-PHB/3-PHV	Volova et al. 2010
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	A		PHB	Lodhi et al. 2011
<i>Gongronella</i> sp.	Z		PHB; PHB-co-PHV	Boyandin et al. 2012a
<i>Paecilomyces</i> sp.	A		PHB; PHB-co-PHV	Boyandin et al. 2012a,b
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	A		PHB; PHB-co-PHV	Boyandin et al. 2012a,b
<i>Trichoderma</i> sp.	A		PHB; PHB-co-PHV	Boyandin et al. 2012a
<i>Acremonium</i> sp.	A		PHB; PHB-co-PHV	Boyandin et al. 2012a
<i>Verticillium</i> sp.	A		PHB; PHB-co-PHV	Boyandin et al. 2012ab
<i>Zygosporium</i> sp.	A		PHB; PHB-co-PHV	Boyandin et al. 2012a
<i>Aureobasidium</i> sp.	A		PHB; PHB-co-PHV	Boyandin et al. 2012b
<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	A	NA25	PHB-co-PHV	Nadhman et al. 2012a
<i>Penicillium expansum</i>	A		PHB	Shivakumar 2012
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	A		PHB	Shivakumar 2013
<i>Penicillium pinophilum</i>	A	ATCC 9644	PHB	Panagiotidou et al. 2014
<i>Penicillium expansum</i>	A		PHB	Gowda and Shivakumar 2015
<i>Acremonium butyri</i>	A		P(3HB)	Volova et al. 2015
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	A	BP-1	P(3HB)	Volova et al. 2015
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	A	BP-2	P(3HB)	Volova et al. 2015
<i>Purpureocillium lilacinum</i>	A		P(3HB)	Volova et al. 2015
<i>Zygosporium masonii</i>	A		P(3HB)	Volova et al. 2015
<i>Verticillium lateritium</i>	A		P(3HB)	Volova et al. 2015
<i>Acremonium recifei</i>	A		P(3HB)	Volova et al. 2015
<i>Gongronella butleri</i>	Z		P(3HB)	Volova et al. 2015
<i>Trichoderma pseudokoningii</i>	A		P(3HB)	Volova et al. 2015
<i>Penicillium oxalicum</i>	A		P(3HB)	Volova et al. 2015

A = Ascomycota, B = Basidiomycota, Z = Zygomycota, C = Chytridiomycota, My-Am = Myxomycota – Amoebozoa.

rine environments recently.

The scarce available data on marine fungi or fungal strains isolated from marine environments that are capable of biodegradation PHAs or PHA-based plastics are summarized in Table 2.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Media

In developing media for fungal growth and detection of PHA biodegradation, three media with a low content of non-PHA organic nutrients were tested comparatively:

1) Glucose-peptone-yeast extract agar (GPY), containing 0.1% glucose, 0.05% peptone, and 0.01% yeast extract (Molitoris and Schaumann 1986).

2) Reduced glucose-peptone-yeast extract agar (rGPY): 0.01% glucose, 0.01% peptone, and 0.01% yeast extract.

3) Basal mineral medium with peptone and yeast extract (MPY): Mineral salts: 0.14% NaNO₃, 0.10% NH₄H₂PO₄, 0.10% KH₂PO₄, 0.06% K₂HPO₄ x 3H₂O, 0.04% MgSO₄ x 7H₂O, 0.02% CaCl₂ x 2H₂O. Organic substances: 0.01% peptone, 0.01% yeast extract. Microelement solution A (1 ml/l medium): 0.40% CuSO₄ x 5H₂O, 0.40% ZnSO₄ x 7H₂O, 0.40% Na₂MoO₄, 0.20% MnSO₄ x H₂O, 0.20% CoCl₂ x 6H₂O, 0.20% H₃BO₃, 0.10% KI, 0.10% Na₂SeO₃ x 5H₂O, 0.10% Na₂WO₄ x 2H₂O, 0.10% KAl(SO₄)₂ x 12H₂O. Microelement solution B (1 ml/l medium): 0.05% FeSO₄ x 7H₂O.

In all cases 1.60% agar and artificial seawater were used

for the preparation of media. The pH was adjusted to 7.0 before autoclaving at 121 °C for 20 min. The composition of artificial seawater was as described earlier (Lorenz and Molitoris 1992) resulting in the following concentrations (weight/volume of distilled water): NaCl - 2.270%, KH₂PO₄ - 0.788%, MgSO₄ x 7H₂O - 0.700%, MgCl₂ x 6H₂O - 0.550%, KCl - 0.065%, NaBr - 0.010%, H₃BO₃ - 0.003%, SrCl₂ x 6H₂O - 0.0015%, C₆H₈O₇ x H₂O - 0.001%. CaCl₂ was added as a separate solution to make a final concentration of 0.15%.

A modified solution of microelements as proposed by Balch and Wolfe (1976) and Balch et al. (1979), was added to give final concentrations of: C₆H₉NO₆ (titriplex I) - 0.0015%, MnSO₄ x H₂O - 0.0005%, Ni(NH₄)₂(SO₄)₂ - 0.0002%, FeSO₄ x 7H₂O - 0.0001%, CoCl₂ x 6H₂O - 0.0001%, ZnSO₄ x 7H₂O - 0.0001%, CuSO₄ x 5H₂O - 0.0001%, KAl(SO₄)₂ x 12H₂O - 0.00001%, Na₂MoO₄ x 2H₂O - 0.00001%, Na₂WO₄ x 2H₂O - 0.00001%, Na₂SeO₃ x 5H₂O - 0.00001%, KI - 0.000005%.

According to the visually recorded the most abundant growth of all tested fungi, the GPY medium was chosen for further experimental work.

Preparation of assay medium

Powdered commercial BIOPOL™ (“Bottle formulation”) (1.00 g) or powdered PHB homopolymer (1.00 g) was suspended in 100 ml of seawater, sonicated for 10 min (Bandelin Sonorex RK 106 S) and autoclaved separately. After sonication for another 10 min, the opaque suspension was added aseptically to 900 ml of hot sterile GPY medium, which was

Table 2. Fungal isolates from marine habitats - degrading poly[(R)-3-hydroxyalkanoates].

Species	Taxon	Strain	Substrate	Reference
<i>Doratomyces</i> sp.	A		PHB, BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991c
<i>Gliomastix</i> sp.	A		PHB, BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991c
<i>Debaryomyces hansenii</i>	Ay		PHB, BIOPOL	Matavulj and Molitoris 1991c
<i>Candida guilliermondii</i>	Ay		PHB, BIOPOL	Neumeier 1994
<i>Debaryomyces hansenii</i>	Ay		PHB, BIOPOL	Neumeier 1994
<i>Rhodosporidium sphaerocarpum</i>	By		PHB, BIOPOL	Neumeier 1994
<i>Aspergillus ustus</i>	A		PHB	Neumeier 1997
<i>Aspergillus ustus</i>	A	M-224	PHB	Gonda et al. 2000
<i>Candida guilliermondii</i>	Ay		PHB	Gonda et al. 2000
<i>Debaryomyces hansenii</i>	Ay		PHB	Gonda et al. 2000
<i>Rhodosporidium sphaerocarpum</i>	B		PHB	Gonda et al. 2000
<i>Gliomastix</i> sp.	A	M-51	BIOPOL	Matavuly and Molitoris 2009
<i>Fusarium merismoides</i>	A	M-46	BIOPOL	Matavuly and Molitoris 2009
<i>Doratomyces</i> sp.	A	M-50	BIOPOL	Matavuly and Molitoris 2009
<i>Asteromyces cruciatus</i>	A	M-1	BIOPOL, PHB	Matavuly and Molitoris 2009
<i>Debaryomyces hansenii</i>	Ay	M-111	BIOPOL, PHB	Matavuly and Molitoris 2009
<i>Debaryomyces hansenii</i>	Ay	M-113	BIOPOL, PHB	Matavuly and Molitoris 2009
<i>Candida guilliermondii</i>	Ay	M-122	BIOPOL	Matavuly and Molitoris 2009
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	B	M-167	BHB	Matavuly and Molitoris 2009
<i>Talaromyces verruculosus</i>	A		PHB	Devi et al. 2014
<i>Syn. Penicillium verruculosum</i>				

A = Ascomycota, B = Basidiomycota, Ay = ascomycetous yeast, By = basidiomycetous yeast.

then sonicated for another 10 min, agitated, cooled to 50 °C and poured into sterile Petri plates or test tubes, which resulted in a fine and evenly distributed turbidity caused by the PHA. During autoclaving of the media, precipitates of mineral salts occurred, which interfered with the readability of the clearing reaction in plates, however no interference occurred in test tubes where the larger particles of the precipitate were allowed to settle before use. To prevent the sedimentation of fine PHA particles during solidification of the media, test tubes were cooled quickly in a cold water bath. Powdered commercial BIOPOL™ was kindly supplied by ICI, England.

Biological materials

One hundred thirty-four pure strains of marine fungi or marine-derived fungi (Culture collection of the Botanical Institute, University of Regensburg), belonging to different systematic and ecological groups (Table 1) were used for testing the three basic media. The halotolerant strain *Penicillium simplicissimum* (IMI 300465) was used as reference strain because of its known high PHB-degrading activity (McLellan and Halling 1988a; Matavulj and Molitoris 1992).

Cultivation

Fungal strains were cultured on GPY agar at 22 °C. Approximately 3 × 3 mm squares from the actively growing area of the agar plates were used as an inoculum. All cultures in test tubes were incubated at 22 °C and approximately 65% relative humidity with a diurnal periodicity of 12 hours light and 12 hours darkness.

Evaluation of degradative activity

Fungal ability to degrade commercial BIOPOL™ and to depolymerize pure PHB homopolymer and use triacetin, was determined by recording the depth of clearing in mm of the opaque media in test tubes at daily (for the first week), or weekly intervals for a period up to 9 weeks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In our work on PHA biodegradation in terrestrial fungi (Matavulj and Molitoris 1992) we recommended using test tubes instead of Petri plates for the PHA clearing test because the clearing reaction on Petri plates may be concealed by the growing mycelium, in particular if working with fastgrowing strains. The same applies here to our work with marine fungi. Since used commercial BIOPOL™ contains several components including PHB and PHV as a heteropolymer (79% PHB, 8% PHV, 9% triacetin, 3% titanium dioxide, 1% boron nitride), it was important to know whether there are differences between media containing PHB-V heteropoly-

mer and media containing pure PHB homopolymer for the purpose of specifying depolymerase activity.

Test results for 134 marine-derived fungi for the biodegradation of commercial BIOPOL™, PHB homopolymer and triacetin are summarized in Table 3.

A total of 134 strains were tested, representing 85 species and (conditionally) 55 genera of different systematic and ecological groups. Interestingly, only 6 strains (4.48%) were found to be able to degrade commercial BIOPOL™, 9 strains (6.72%) depolymerized PHB homopolymer, and 124 strains (92.53%) were able to use triacetin as the sole carbon source. This is in sharp contrast with our results using terrestrial fungi, where approximately 55% were able to degrade commercial BIOPOL™, and nearly 68% depolymerized PHB homopolymer (Matavulj and Molitoris 1992). Triacetin was also degraded by more than 90% of the terrestrial fungi tested. The easy degradability of triacetin could be an important initial step in the destruction of this plastic material in nature, especially under oligotrophic marine conditions.

Mergaert and Swings (1996), using polyhydroxyalkanoates as another pollutant, were unable to isolate any marine fungus able to degrade these substances *in situ*. Using pure fungal cultures, Matavulj and Molitoris (1991c), Neumeier (1994a), and Molitoris et al. (1995) also found considerably less marine isolates of filamentous fungi and yeasts (vs. terrestrial) capable of PHB biodegradation. One possible explanation for this disparity lies in the fact that almost all producers of PHAs are isolated from freshwater or terrestrial environments, while producers of PHAs from marine environments are almost unknown.

The results of a study by Neumeier (1997) showed less degradation of PHB by marine and terrestrial isolates of *Aspergillus ustus* (T-221, M-224) in artificial seawater vs. the same terrestrial isolate of *A. ustus* (T-221) grown in freshwater medium under otherwise identical conditions (GPY medium with PHB). Even more convincing is the failure of marine yeast isolates studied to degrade PHB in artificial seawater medium since on solid freshwater medium they all degraded PHB, at least in the clearing test (Neumeier 1994). The negative effects of salinity on the biodegradation of different substrates by fungi have been reported earlier. Rohrmann (1993) noticed a decrease in the degradation of wood with increasing media salinity. Decreased growth, substrate degradation and enzyme activity with increasing salinity was also found by Kurchenko et al. (1998), and Molitoris et al. (1998).

A study of bacterial biodegradation of PHAs by Jendrossek et al. (1993) revealed that only approximately 10% of aerobic PHB-utilizing bacteria were also able to degrade pure PHV-homopolymers. Furthermore, Doi et al. (1990) reported that the rate of polyester degradation by extracellular PHA depolymerase purified from the bacterium *Alcaligenes eutrophus*, was strongly dependent on the composition of the polyester. They observed that the presence of 3-hy-

droxyvalerate units significantly retarded the degradation of the polyester as compared with the rate of pure PHB degradation. Also, attenuation of the biodegradability of PHB by a lignin-rich filler used for production of bio-based blends was reported recently (Angelini et al. 2014).

Another important question is whether PHA-degrading activity correlates with the systematic or ecologic groups of fungi investigated. Because of the low number of active strains in marine fungal isolates, it is difficult to obtain statistically significant correlations. However, from Table 3 it can be seen that biodegradation activities are not evenly distributed among the different groups of tested marine-derived fungal species. Table 3 seems to indicate that PHA-degrading activity in marine fungal isolates is rather low among the Ascomycotina (BIOPOL™ – 5.71%, PHB – 6.67%) as well as in the group of Basidiomycotina (BIOPOL™ – 0.00%, PHB – 6.89%).

Considering the distribution of PHA-degrading activity among several members of a given genus or a given species, one can see from Table 3 that out of five strains of *Asteromyces cruciatus* tested, only the strain M-1 was able to degrade both commercial BIOPOL™ and pure PHB. Out of 9 strains of the genus *Candida*, only one strain of *Candida guilliermondii* (M-122) depolymerised PHB, but not commercial BIOPOL™. The yeast *Debaryomyces hansenii* was represented in our screen by 6 strains, of which only two showed the ability to degrade both PHB and BIOPOL™.

Investigation of 29 isolates belonging to Basidiomycotina, representing 4 genera (*Cryptococcus*, *Nia*, *Rhodospiridium* and *Sporobolomyces*) and 15 species, showed that only one strain of *Nia vibrissa* (M-167) (Agaricales) and one strain of *Rhodospiridium sphaerocarpum* species (M-185)

(Sporidiobolales) were able to depolymerize PHB, but not commercial BIOPOL™. Earlier we reported that among 65 investigated terrestrial basidiomycetous mushroom strains, *Collybia peronata*, *Lentinus edodes*, *Pleurotus ostreatus*, *Serpula lacrymans*, and *Polyporus circinatus* were able to degrade BIOPOL (Matavulj and Molitoris, 1991a, 1992).

CONCLUSION

According to the data presented, it turned out that the biodegradation capacity of marine-derived fungal population against tested PHB and BIOPOL™ was pretty poor (4.5% degraded BIOPOL™ and 6.7% depolymerized pure PHB). This is in contrast to the results obtained from investigation of terrestrial fungi (more than 55% active). Moreover, our data indicate that in marine-derived fungi this characteristic is not related to taxonomic character of a particular species or genera, nor is it a feature of certain ecological groups. In contrast, PHA biodegradation activity seems rather to be a physiological characteristic of individual “physiological strains” of the studied marine-derived fungal species.

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Table 3. Test results for fungi isolated from marine environments on the degradation of BIOPOL™, PHB homopolymer and triacetin.

Species	Authority	Taxon	Origin	Code	Rg Code	Marine	Substrate	BP	PHB	Ta
<i>Acremonium furcatum</i>	Moreau & R. Moreau ex Gams, 1969	A	KMPB	H 750	M-039	MI	sand/beam	-	-	+
<i>Acremonium potronii</i>	Vuillemin, 1910	A	KMPB	H 707	M-037	MI	sand/beam	-	-	+
<i>Acremonium</i> sp.	-	A	KMPB	H 2046	M-038	MI	sediment	-	-	+
<i>Amylocarpus encephaloides</i>	Currey, 1859	A	PP	# 1002	M-141	MI	wood	-	-	-
<i>Ascomyces indeterminatus</i>	-	A	JK	R 13/2	M-066	-	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Ascomyces indeterminatus</i>	-	A	KMPB	H 344	M-011	-	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Asteromyces cruciatus</i>	Moreau & Moreau ex Hennebert, 1962	A	KMPB	H 54a	M-001	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Asteromyces cruciatus</i>	Moreau & Moreau ex Hennebert, 1962	A	KMPB	H 76	M-084	MI	foam	-	-	+
<i>Asteromyces cruciatus</i>	Moreau & Moreau ex Hennebert, 1962	A	URB	SR 2	M-149	MI	foam	-	-	+
<i>Asteromyces cruciatus</i>	Moreau & Moreau ex Hennebert, 1962	A	JK	3678	M-153	MI	sand/beam	-	-	+
<i>Asteromyces cruciatus</i>	Moreau & Moreau ex Hennebert, 1962	A	URB	H 55	M-181	MI	wood/dune	-	-	+
<i>Aureobasidium pullulans</i>	(de Bary) G. Arnaud (1918)	Ay	PP	698	M-156	FM	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Bioniospora comiculata</i>	Schaumann, 1972	A	KMPB	H 691	M-012	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Camarosporium roumeguieri</i>	Saccardo, 1880	A	JK	3905	M-076	MI	<i>Salicornia</i> sp. leaves	-	-	-
<i>Pichia guilliermondii</i>	Wickerham, 1966	Ay	SC	NS-76-148	M-118	FM	seawater	-	-	+
Anamorph: <i>Candida guilliermondii</i>	(Castellani) Langeron & Guerra, 1938									
<i>Pichia guilliermondii</i>	Wickerham, 1966	Ay	SC	NS-76-153	M-119	FM	sea gull liver	-	-	+
Anamorph: <i>Candida guilliermondii</i>	(Castellani) Langeron & Guerra, 1938									
<i>Pichia guilliermondii</i>	Wickerham, 1966	Ay	SC	NS-76-155	M-120	FM	sea gull liver	-	-	+
Anamorph: <i>Candida guilliermondii</i>	(Castellani) Langeron & Guerra, 1938									
<i>Pichia guilliermondii</i>	Wickerham, 1966	Ay	SC	NS-76-266	M-121	FM	seawater	-	-	+
Anamorph: <i>Candida guilliermondii</i>	(Castellani) Langeron & Guerra, 1938									
<i>Pichia guilliermondii</i>	Wickerham, 1966	Ay	SC	NS-76-283	M-122	FM	seawater	-	-	+
Anamorph: <i>Candida guilliermondii</i>	(Castellani) Langeron & Guerra, 1938									
<i>Pichia guilliermondii</i>	Wickerham, 1966	Ay	SC	NS-76-299	M-123	FM	seawater	-	-	+
Anamorph: <i>Candida guilliermondii</i>	(Castellani) Langeron & Guerra, 1938									
<i>Pichia guilliermondii</i>	Wickerham, 1966	Ay	SC	NS-76-167	M-148	FM	seawater	-	-	+
Anamorph: <i>Candida guilliermondii</i>	(Castellani) Langeron & Guerra, 1938									
<i>Candida sobophila</i>	(Nakase) Meyer & Yarrow, 1978	Ay	URM	Cy4/1b	M-186	MI	Vulcanic rock	-	-	+
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	(Castellani) Berkhout, 1923	Ay	SC	NS-76-162	M-124	FM	Sea gull gut content	-	-	+
<i>Carbospaerella leptosphaerioides</i>	I. Schmidt, 1969	A	PP	4810	M-189	MI	Driftwood	-	-	+
<i>Carbospaerella leptosphaerioides</i>	I. Schmidt, 1969	A	PP	4804	M-190	MI	Driftwood	-	-	+
<i>Acremonium sclerotigenum</i>	(M.&R. Moreau ex Valenta) W.Gams, 1972	A	KMPB	H 724	M-040	MI	Sand beach	-	-	+
An.: <i>Cephalosporium sclerotigenum</i>	M. & R. Moreau ex Valenta, 1948									
<i>Ceriosporopsis circumvestita</i>	(Kohlm.) Kohlm., 1972	A	PP	0724	M-207	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Ceriosporopsis halima</i>	Linder in Barghoorn & Linder, 1944	A	URB	M-178	M-178	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Ceriosporopsis halima</i>	Linder in Barghoorn & Linder, 1944	A	URB	M-179	M-179	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Chaetomium rampiposum</i>	Schaumann, 1973	A	KMPB	H 890/2	M-013	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	-	A	KMPB	H 2076	M-55	MI	Sediment	-	-	+
<i>Cirrenalia macrocephala</i>	(Kohlm.) Meyers & RT Moore, 1960	A	KMPB	H 210	M-002	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Cirrenalia macrocephala</i>	(Kohlm.) Meyer, & RT Moore, 1960	A	JK	6073	M-159	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Cirrenalia pygmaea</i>	Kohlmeier, 1966	A	PP	# 1036	M-138	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Cirrenalia tropicalis</i>	Kohlmeier, 1968	A	PP	# 1031	M-139	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i>	(Fresen.) de Vries, 1952	A	URM	1/1	M-201	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i>	(Fresen.) de Vries, 1952	A	URM	1/3	M-203	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i>	(Fresen.) de Vries, 1952	A	URM	2/1	M-204	MI	Ni	-	-	+

Table 3. Test results for fungi isolated from marine environments on the degradation of BIOPOL™, PHB homopolymer and triacetin.

Species	Authority	Taxon	Origin	Code	Rg Code	Marine	Substrate	BP	PHB	Ta
<i>Cladosporium herbarum</i>	(Pers.) Link ex S. F. Gray, 1816	A	URM	1/2	M-202	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Cladosporium herbarum</i>	(Pers.) Link ex S. F. Gray, 1816	A	URM	2/2	M-205	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Coralliospora colossa</i>	Nakagiri & Tokura, 1988	A	PP	4794	M-191	MI	Driftwood	-	-	+
<i>Coralliospora lacera</i>	(Linder in Bargh & Lind) Kohlm., 1962	A	JK	3897	M-058	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Coralliospora maritima</i>	Werdermann, 1922	A	KMPB	H671	M-015	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Coralliospora maritima</i>	Werdermann, 1922	A	JK	4414	M-059	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Coralliospora micritima</i>	Werdermann, 1922	A	URB	SR 8	M-150	MI	Sand	-	-	+
<i>Coralliospora maritima</i>	Werdermann, 1922	A	URB	H12/1	M-182	MI	Wood/Sandy beach	-	-	+
<i>Coralliospora quinqueseptata</i>	Nakagiri ex Tokura, 1988	A	URB	M1206	M-206	MI	Ni	-	-	-
<i>Coralliospora trifurcata</i>	(Höhlk) Kohlm., 1962	A	JK	4423/1	M-087	MI	Detritus	-	-	+
<i>Cryptococcus albidus</i>	(Saito) Skinner, 1950	By	JF	ML2604	M-103	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Curvularia</i> sp.		A	PP	520	M-155	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Cytospora rhizophorae</i>	Kohlmeier & Kohlmeier, 1971	A	JK	5241	M-176	MI	Ni	-	-	-
<i>Debaryomyces hanseni</i>	(Zopf) Lodder & Kreger-van Rij (1984)	Ay	SC	NS-75-9	M-111	FM	Seawater	+	+	+
<i>Debaryomyces hanseni</i>	(Zopf) Lodder & Kreger-van Rij (1984)	Ay	SC	NS-75-10	M-112	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Debaryomyces hanseni</i>	(Zopf) Lodder & Kreger-van Rij (1984)	Ay	SC	NS-75-11	M-113	FM	Seawater	+	+	+
<i>Debaryomyces hanseni</i>	(Zopf) Lodder & Kreger-van Rij (1984)	Ay	SC	NS-75-21	M-114	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Debaryomyces hanseni</i>	(Zopf) Lodder & Kreger-van Rij (1984)	Ay	SC	NS-75-35	M-115	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Debaryomyces hanseni</i>	(Zopf) Lodder & Kreger-van Rij (1984)	Ay	SC	NS-75-60	M-116	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Dendryphiella salina</i>	(Sutherland) Pugh & Nicot., 1964	A	kmpb	H/800/1	M-003	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Dendryphiella salina</i>	(Sutherland) Pugh & Nicot., 1964	A	jk	2	M-007	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Dendryphiella salina</i>	(Sutherland) Pugh & Nicot., 1964	A	urb	SR 22	M-151	MI	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Dendryphiella salina</i>	(Sutherland) Pugh & Nicot., 1964	A	urb	H3	M-183	MI	Wood/Sandy beach	-	-	+
<i>Diclyosporium pelagicum</i>	(Linder) Hugh. ex EBG Jones, 1963	A	KMPB	H652	M-004	MI	Ni	-	-	-
<i>Doratomyces</i> sp.		A	KMPB	H2086	M-050	MI	Sediment	+	+	+
<i>Drechslera halodes</i>	(Drechsler) Subram. & Bl. Jain, 1966	A	JK	4094	M-062	MI	Detritus	-	-	+
<i>Fusarium merismoides</i>	Corda, 1838	A	KMPB	H635	M-046	MI	Sand/beach	+	+	+
<i>Fusarium sambucinum</i>	Fückel, 1870	A	KMPB	H796	M-045	MI	Sand/beach	-	-	+
Teleomorph: <i>Gibberella pulicaris</i>	(Fr.) Sacc. (1877)									
<i>Gliomastix</i> sp.		A	KMPB	H2001	M-051	MI	Sediment	+	+	+
<i>Halosarphaea rathnagriensis</i>	Patil & Borse, 1982	A	PP	1907	M-193	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Halosarphaea trullifera</i>	(Kohlm.) Jones, Moss & Cuomo, 1983	A	PP	4912	M-194	MI	Driftwood	-	-	+
<i>Halosarphaea trullifera</i>	(Kohlm.) Jones, Moss & Cuomo, 1983	A	PP	4913	M-195	MI	Driftwood	-	-	+
<i>Halosphaeriopsis mediosetigera</i>	(Cribb & Cribb) Johnson, 1958	A	URB	M180	M-180	MI	Driftwood	-	-	+
<i>Humicola alapolanella</i>	Meyers & Moore, 1960	A	KMPB	H441	M-005	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Leptosphaeria australiensis</i>	(Cribb & Cribb) G.C. Hughes, 1969	A	JK	4482/1	M-065	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Leptosphaeria obiones</i>	(Crouan & Crouan) Saccardo, 1883	A	JK	3904	M-090	MI	<i>Spartina alterniflora</i>	-	-	+
<i>Lignicola laevis</i>	Höhlk, 1955	A	KMPB	H36	M-016	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Lignicola laevis</i>	Höhlk, 1955	A	PP	3239	M-196	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Lindra obtusa</i>	Nakagiri & Tubaki, 1983	A	PP	4943	M-197	MI	Driftwood	-	-	+
<i>Lulworthia lignoarenaria</i>	Koch & Jones, 1984	A	PP	#920	M-142	MI	Driftwood	-	-	+
<i>Lulworthia</i> sp.		A	KMPB	H622	M-018	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Lulworthia</i> sp.		A	JK	4298/1	M-068	MI	Wood/mangrove	-	-	+
<i>Macrophoma</i> sp.		A	JK	4342	M-069	MI	Propprot/Rhizophora	-	-	+

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<i>Marinosphaeria mangrovei</i>	Hyde, 1988	A	PP	3820	M-198	MI	Mangrove	-	-	+
<i>Microascus senegalensis</i>	von Arx, 1975	A	JK	4288/2	M-071	MI	Wood/mangrove	-	-	+
<i>Microascus senegalensis</i>	von Arx, 1975	A	JK	4288/6	M-072	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Microascus trigonosporus</i>	Emmons & Dodge	A	KMPB	H680	M-019	OM	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Monodictys pelagica</i>	(Johnson) Jones, 1963	A	KMPB	H 106	M-006	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Teleomorph: Nereiospora cristata</i>	(Kohlm.) Jones, Johnson & Moss, 1983	A	KMPB	H 580	M-007	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Monodictys pelagic</i>	(Johnson) Jones, 1963	A	JK	516	M-070	MI	Piling	-	-	+
<i>Teleomorph: Nereiospora cristata</i>	(Kohlm.) Jones, Johnson & Moss, 1983	A	KMPB	H 6745	M-052	MI	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Monodictys sp.</i>	Grane & Shearer, 1986	A	PP	4892	M-208	MI	Mangrove	-	-	+
<i>Nais alitra</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	ATCC	34606	M-021	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	JK	5071	M-154	MI	Propropert/Rhizophora	-	-	-
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	PP	2770	M-170	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	PP	2772	M-171	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	PP	1071	M-161	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	PP	2765	M-167	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	PP	2767	M-168	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	PP	2768	M-169	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	PP	1068	M-172	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	JFO	32088	M-173	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	JFO	32089	M-174	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	ATCC	34606	M-175	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Nia vibrissa</i>	Moore & Meyers, 1959	B	URB	OD 3	M-187	MI	Submerg. pine wood	-	-	+
<i>Orbimyces spectabilis</i>	Linder, 1944	A	PP	# 517	M-140	MI	Wood	-	-	-
<i>Pestalotia</i> sp.	Anastasiou, 1963	A	PP	3641	M-157	MI	Driftwood	-	-	+
<i>Periconia prolifica</i>	(Lagerberg & Melin) Conant, 1937	A	PP	3508	M-199	MI	Scots pine wood	-	-	+
<i>Phialophora fastigiata</i>	(Kidd & Beaumont) McColloch, 1944	A	KMPB	H 708	M-041	MI	Sand/Beach	-	-	+
<i>Phialophora malorum</i>	(Kidd & Beaumont) W. Gams, 2000	A	KMPB	H 737b	M-042	MI	Sand/Beach	-	-	+
<i>Phoma</i> sp.	(Höhnk) Kohlmeier, 1961	A	KMPB	H 8	M-053	MI	Pine wood	-	-	+
<i>Remispora hamata</i>	Fell, Hunter & Tallman, 1973	A	KMPB	H 14	M-047	MI	Ni	-	-	-
<i>Rhodosporidium bisporidii</i>	(Fell, Hunt.&Tallm.)Oberw.&Bandoni, 1983	By	JF	ML 2498	M-099	OM	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Syn. Cystoflobasidium bisporidii</i>	Fell, Hunter & Tallmann, 1973;	By	JF	ML 2499	M-100	OM	Zooplankton	-	-	+
<i>Rhodosporidium capitatum</i>	(Fell, Hunt.&Tallm.)Oberw.& Bandoni, 1983	By	JF	ML 2505	M-102	OM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Syn. Cystoflobasidium capitatum</i>	Fell, Hunter & Tallmann, 1973	By	JF	# 2904	M-081	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Rhodosporidium dacyroidium</i>	Newell & Hunter, 1970	By	JF	ML 2500	M-101	OM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Rhodosporidium diobovatum</i>	Fell & Hunter, 1970	By	JF	# 2920	M-080	OM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Rhodosporidium malvinellum</i>	Newell & Fell, 1970	By	URM	M 184	M-184	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Rhodosporidium sphaerocarpum</i>	Newell & Fell, 1970	By	URM	M 185	M-185	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Rhodosporidium sphaerocarpum</i>	Banno, 1967	By	JF	ML 2965	M-108	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Rhodosporidium tenuioides</i>	(Saito) Loddner, 1934	By	JF	ML 2969	M-104	FM	Seawater	-	-	+

Table 3. Test results for fungi isolated from marine environments on the degradation of BIOPOL™, PHB homopolymer and triacetin.

Species	Authority	Taxon	Origin	Code	Rg Code	Marine	Substrate	BP	PHB	Ta
<i>Rhodotorula glutinis</i>	(Fresenius) Harrison, 1928	By	JF	ML 2919	M-106	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Rhodotorula graminis</i>	Di Menna, 1958	By	JF	ML 2925	M-107	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Rhodotorula minuta</i>	(Saito) Harrison, 1928	By	JF	# 2911	M-082	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Rhodotorula mucilaginosa</i>	(A. Jörg.) Harrison, 1928;	By	JF	" 2918	M-083	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
Syn. <i>Rhodotorula rubra</i>	(Demme) Lodder, 1934									
<i>Saroyella paucispora</i>	(Cribb & Cribb) Koch, 1982	A	JK	4478/9	M-073	MI	<i>Hibiscus tiliac.</i> wood	-	-	+
<i>Sporobolomyces salmonicolor</i>	(Fisch. & Breb.) Kuyv. & CB Niel, 1924	By	JF	# 2944	M-085	FM	Seawater	-	-	+
<i>Trichocladium ochrasporum</i>	(Mayers & Moore) Dixon, 1968	A	JK	F 92	M-079	MI	Ni	-	-	+
<i>Trichocladium ochrasporum</i>	(Mayers & Moore) Dixon, 1968	A	URB	M 177	M-177	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Variosporeina ramulosa</i>	Meyers & Kohlmeier, 1965	A	JK	113	M-074	MI	<i>Zostera marina</i>	-	-	-
<i>Verruculina enalia</i>	(Kohlm.) Kohlm. & Volk. - Kohlm., 1990	A	PP	3019	M-192	MI	Mangrove wood	-	-	+
<i>Verticillium lecanii</i>	(Zimmermann) Viegas, 1939;									
Syn. <i>Lecanicillium lecanii</i>	(Zimm.) R. Zare & W. Gams, 2001	A	KMPB	H 889	M-054	MI	Rhizosphaera	-	-	+
<i>Zalerion maritimum</i>	(Linder) Anastasiou, 1963;									
Teleomorph: <i>Lulworthia uniseptata</i>	Nakagiri, 1984	A	JK	4779	M-160	MI	Driftwood	-	-	+
<i>Zalerion maritimum</i>	(Linder) Anastasiou, 1963;									
Teleomorph: <i>Lulworthia uniseptata</i>	Nakagiri, 1984	A	PP	1329	M-163	MI	Wood	-	-	+
<i>Zalerion maritimum</i>	(Linder) Anastasiou, 1963;									
Teleomorph: <i>Lulworthia uniseptata</i>	Nakagiri, 1984	A	URB	M 209	M-209	MI	Wood	-	-	+

Classification: A = Ascomycota, B = Basidiomycota, Ay = ascomycetous yeast, By = basidiomycetous yeast.
 Origin: ATCCO American Type Culture Collection; JF = J. Fell, Miami USA; JFO = A. Nakagiri, Osaka, Japan; JK = J. Kohlmeier, Morehead City, USA; PP = E.B.G. Jones, Portsmouth, UK; SC = S. Crow, Athens, USA; URB = Collection of the Botanical Institute of the University of Regensburg, Germany; URM = K.O. Sterter, Collection of the Microbiological Institute of the University of Regensburg, Germany.

Orig. code: Original code number of supplier of culture.

Rg. Code: Code number of the Regensburg University Collection.

Marine: Marine strains or marine isolates = MI, unless specified: OM = obligate marine, FM = facultative marine.

Substrate: Ni = No information available.

Degradation of: BIOPOL™, PHB = poly-β-hydroxybutyrate homopolymer, Ta = triacetin.

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